

Diversity of Spontaneous Vegetation on Post-Industrial Sites – Importance in Reclamation Process

G. Woźniak, R. Rostański & E. Sierka University of Silesia, PL

G. Aschan & H. Pfan University of Duisburg-Essen, GER

ABSTRACT

Industrial wasteland is a typical element of the landscape of all the industrialised regions in Europe. There are many examples from Poland as well as from other European countries that post-industrial sites have been undergone natural colonisation and succession to establish in some cases ecosystems of greater biological diversity than the original ecosystems.

The post-industry sites regardless of any reclamation carried out, undergo natural successional processes. The respective biological diversity (number of species, and number of plant assemblages) reflects the micro-variety of the specific habitat.

This paper summarizes the results of investigations, which have been carried out since 1989 on coal mine water sedimentation pools in the Upper Silesia Industry Region. The aim of this study is to demonstrate the diversity of spontaneous plant communities recorded on post-industrial waste sites.

In the course of the long time fieldwork, plant assemblages representing nine phytosociological groups have been identified.

INTRODUCTION

The industrial wasteland is the typical element of the landscape of all the industrialised regions in Europe. Management of such sites has become an important environmental problem. On one hand because of the industrial activity the natural plant cover and land relief have been changed or even destroyed on the other hand new exceptional habitats has been created. The industrial sites regardless of any reclamation carried out, undergo natural process (succession), that is the result of ecology in its basic meaning - the interrelationship between living organisms and their immediate wasteland habitat. The biological diversity (number of species, and number of plant assemblages) reflects the micro-variety of the specific habitat. The multivariate environmental conditions at the postindustrial sites are the obvious but unfortunately very complex factor of wasteland reclamation.

There are some studies describing vegetation of single or few sites; pit-coal mining heaps (Cabała, Sypień 1987 [4]; Jochimsen 1991 [7]; Jochimsen et al. 1995 [8]; Rostański, 1996 [13], 1997b [15], 1998a [16], 2000a [18], 2000b [19], 2000c [20], Rostański 2001 [21], Rostański, Trueman 2001 [22]), iron and non-ferrous metallurgy heaps (Rostański A. 1997a [14], 1998b [17]), brown coal mining sedimentation pools (Balcerkiewicz, Pawlak 1990 [1], 1991 [2], Krzaklewski 1979 [10]), sand pits (Czylok, Rahmanow 1999 [6], Kompała 1997 [9], Szwedo et al. 1995 [24]), and coal-mine sedimentation pools (Woźniak 1998a [28], 1998b [29], 2000 [30], 2001 [31]), solvay process tips (Cohn et al. 2001 [5], Trzcińska-Tacik 1966 [26], Wilkoń-Michalska, Sokół 1968 [27]), but there is still lack of comprehensive prescription how to perform reclamation according to the sustainability idea.

The aim of this presentation is to describe and analyse the variety of spontaneously created plant assemblages.

METHODS

The investigations have been carried out since 1989 on post-industrial waste sites in the Upper Silesia Industry Region . More than one thousand phytosociological relevés were made in order to document the plant communities' occurrence (Braun-Blanquet 1951 [3]). The recognition of plant communities based on characteristic combination of species (Szafer et al. 1986 [23]). The relevés were arranged in tables according to Matuszkiewicz 1984 [11] "Przewodnik do oznaczania zbiorowisk roślinnych Polski" (A guidebook for recognition of Polish plant communities). To quantify the variety of species composition on the post – industrial sites the method for classifying the vegetation of natural and semi-natural habitats was used (Matuszkiewicz, 1984 [11]).

RESULTS

In the course of investigations it has been stated that the flora and vegetation of post-industry sites represents a high level of diversity, which is shown in the list below. The plant communities of natural and semi-natural habitats are classified to plant community classes. Each class comprises plant assemblages occurring on one kind of habitat as following:

Thlaspietea rotundifolii collects the pioneer plant communities occurring on mobile or weak stabilised slide rocks.

Bidentetea tripartiti includes communities, that are built by moderate nitrophilous annual plants occurring on water reservoirs which dry out in summer.

Plantaginetea maioris includes plant assemblages of annual and perennial weeds most often creeping occurring on soils of low porosity and poor oxygen conditions in the rhizosphere (at least periodically).

Artemisietea vulgaris represents a unit, which contains nitrophilous communities built by herbs and high perennials and creepers of ruderal habitats and sites round the water reservoirs.

Potamogetonetea includes rooted and not rooted water species, which build the communities growing in deep 2-3 m or shallow water reservoirs.

Phragmitetea comprises poor in species reed and sedge rushes with single big perennials naturally occurring in the coastal zone of inland water reservoirs

Sedo-Scleranthethea includes European plant communities of psammophilous and siliceous -rocky grasslands created by narrow-leaved xerothermic grasses with the participation of rosette plants, many xerophyte and succulent species

Molinio-Arrhenatheretea class embodies semi-natural and antropogenic turfy meadow communities and pastures on mesophilous and eutrophic, not swamping mineral soils; those communities are common in all over the Europe

Analysing the data in the list above it is quite evident how the single plant species create groups of similar habitat requirements. There is a group representing the pioneer plants of weak stabilised rocks. The plant assemblages of the water level changeable nitrophilous habitats do not create a distinct group but there are dispersed among patches classified to *Potamogetonetea* and *Phragmitetea*. The species representing the ruderal plant communities of the *Plantaginetea maioris* and *Artemisietea* class are obviously present in many relevés. Those plants are typical of antropogenic changed sites. Many meadow plants are growing in those phytocoenoses. Water plants communities are present in these parts of the sites where the suitable habitat conditions are available. General, the rush plant communities prefer similar habitat properties, however they are more flexible and able to sustain short time of drought. The sand (psammophilous) grasslands and the peatbog phytocoenoses create the vegetation of different habitats. The field investigations show that their patches can occur in short distance from each other. If the habitat condition remains constant they grow and create a diversified mosaic of vegetation patches.

Diversity of plant communities on post industrial sites

Plant communities and assemblages
Class: <i>Potametea</i>
<i>Potamogetonum natantis</i> Soó 1927
Class: <i>Phragmiti-Magnocaricetea</i>
<i>Phragmitetum communis</i> /Gams 1927/ Schmale 1939
<i>Glycerietum maximae</i> Hueck 1931
<i>Typhetum latifoliae</i> Soo 1927
<i>Typhetum angustifoliae</i> (Allorge 1922) Soó 1927
<i>Sparganietum erecti</i> Roll 38
<i>Scirpetum maritimi</i> (Br.-Bl.1931) R.Tx. 1937
<i>Eleocharidetum palustris</i> Schennikov 1919
<i>Alismo-Glycerietum fluitantis</i> (Fal.1966) Podb. 1969
<i>Caricetum rostratae</i> Rübel 1912
<i>Iridetum pseudoacori</i> Eggler 1933 n.n.
<i>Phalaridetum arundinaceae</i> Libb. 1931
Class: <i>Thlaspietea rotundifolii</i>
community with <i>Myricaria germanica</i>
Class: <i>Scheuchzerio-Caricetea fuscae</i>
<i>Juncetum alpini</i> (Oberd. 57) Phil. 1960
community with <i>Eriophorum latifolium</i>
community with <i>Eriophorum angustifolium</i>
community with <i>Menyanthes trifoliata</i>
community with <i>Juncus articulatus</i>
Class: <i>Asteretea tripolium</i>
<i>Puccinellio-Spergularietum salinae</i> (Feekes 1936) R.Tx. et Volk 1937
Class: <i>Bidentetea tripartiti</i>
<i>Bidenti-Polygonetum hydropiperis</i> (Miljan 1933) Lohm. ap. Tx. 1950
<i>Chenopodietum glauco-rubri</i> (Weevers 1940) Lohm. 1950 ap. Oberd. 1957
<i>Bidenti-Ranunculetum scelerati</i> (Miljan 1933) R.Tx.1937
<i>Bidenti-Atriplicetum hastatae</i> (Poli et J.Tx. 1960) Runge 1961
community with <i>Bidens tripartita</i>

Class: <i>Isoëto-Nanojuncetea</i>
community with <i>Juncus bufonius</i> (Passarge 1964) Philippi 1968
community with <i>Plantago intermedia</i>
community with <i>Centaureum erythrea</i> subsp. <i>erythrea</i>
Class: <i>Koelerio-Coryneporetea</i>
<i>Sclerantho-Herniarietum glabrae</i> Glow. 1988
Class: <i>Stellarietea mediae</i>
<i>Salsoletum ruthenicae</i> Phil. 1971
<i>Chenopodietum botrys</i>
<i>Digitarietum ischaemi</i> R.Tx. et Prsg. (1942) 1950
<i>Vicietum tetraspermae</i> Krusem. et Vlieg 1939 em Kornaś
community with <i>Diploaxis muralis</i>
Class: <i>Artemisietea</i>
<i>Echio-Melilotetum</i> Tx. 1942
<i>Poo compressae-Tussilaginetum</i> (Tx. 1928 n.n.) Libb. 1930 nom. invers.
<i>Arctio-Artemisietum vulgaris</i> (Felf. 1942) Oberd. ex Seybold et Th. Müller 1972
<i>Artemisio-Tanacetum vulgaris</i> Br.-Bl. 1931 corr. 1949 em. Oberd. ex Seybold et Th. Müller 1972
<i>Convolvulo-Agropyretum</i> Felf. (1942) 1943.
<i>Rubo-Calamagrostietum epigeji</i> Coste (1974) 1975
<i>Eupatorietum cannabini</i> Tx. 1937
community with <i>Solidago canadensis-Solidago gigantea</i>
community with <i>Reynoutria japonica</i>
community with <i>Humulus lupulus</i>
community with <i>Medicago lupulina</i>
community with <i>Reseda lutea</i>
community with <i>Chamaenerion palustre</i>
community with <i>Callendula officinalis</i>
community with <i>Brassica napus</i>
Class: <i>Polygono-Poëtea</i>
<i>Polygono-Matricarietum matricarioidis</i> (Siss. 1969) Tx. 1972
<i>Poëtum annuae</i> Gams 1927

Class: <i>Molinio-Arrhenatheretea</i>
<i>Potentilletum anserinae</i> (Rapaics 27) Pass. 1964
<i>Ranunculo-Alopecuretum geniculati</i> R.Tx. (1937) 1950
<i>Scirpetum silvatici</i> Ralski 1931
community with <i>Agrostis stolonifera</i>
community with <i>Hordeum jubatum</i> ,
community with <i>Eleocharis uniglumis</i>
community with <i>Rumex crispus</i>

CONCLUSIONS

The plant-cover that develops in the course of spontaneous succession is best adjusted to the prevailing environmental conditions. The reclamation plans (at least of the coal mine heaps and sedimentation pools) should consider spontaneous succession as one of practicable reclamation and restoration strategy. This method will never fail and is cost-efficient, however it needs time.

It seems that there is a need to collect a lot of biological and environmental data in order to get the knowledge how to manage various types of industrial wastelands. For some sites it is possible to consider them as bare mineral land exposed to natural colonisation (similar to a site of natural retreat of glaciers). In such cases the biological potential is of crucial importance in the recovery of systems after natural disasters. So the biological potential (spontaneous biological diversity) is important for such proposes like re-establishment of self-sustaining, functioning ecosystems in restorations. This biological potential is usually referred to as biodiversity of a system. The diversity is expressed by the number and abundance of species of all type within a particular functional unit.

REFERENCES

- [1] Balcerkiewicz S., Pawlak G. 1990. Zbiorowiska roślinne zwałowiska zewnętrznego Pątnów-Józwin w Konińskim Zagłębiu Węgla Brunatnego. - *Badania Fizjograficzne nad Polską Zachodnią*, Ser. Botanika 40: 57-106.
- [2] Balcerkiewicz S., Pawlak G. 1991. Zarastanie zwałowiska zewnętrznego kopalni odkrywkowej węgla brunatnego w aspekcie analizy florystyczno-ekologicznej występujących tam zbiorowisk roślinnych - *Archiwum Ochrony Środowiska* 2: 7-20.
- [3] Braun-Blanquet 1951. *Pflanzensoziologie*. Springer – Verlag, Wien

- [4] Cabała S., Sypień B. 1987. Rozwój szaty roślinnej na wybranych zwałowiskach kopalń węgla kamiennego GOP. - *Archiwum Ochrony Środowiska* 3,4: 7-20.
- [5] Cohn V. J., Rostański A., Tokarska-Guzik B., Trueman I.C., Woźniak G. 2001. The flora and vegetation of an old solvay process tip in Jaworzno (Upper Silesia, Poland). *Acta Soc. Bot. Pol.* 70(1): 47-60.
- [6] Czyłok A., Rahamanow O., 1999. The initial stages of succession with variegated horsetail *Equisetum variegatum* Schleich on wet sand of surface excavations, In: *Anthropogenic aspects of geographical environment transformation*, [Ed]. J. Szabo, J. Wach, L. Kossuth, University of Silesia, Debrecen-Sosnowiec s.81.
- [7] Jochimsen M. E. A. 1991. Vegetationsökologische Gesichtspunkte zur Begrünung von Bergematerial. In: Wiggering H., Kerth M. (Ed.) *Bergehalden im Ruhrgebiet. Beanspruchung und Veränderung eines industriellen Ballungsraumes*, Vieweg, Braunschweig-Wiesbaden: 155-162.
- [8] Jochimsen M. E. A., Hartung J., Fischer I. 1995. Spontane und künstliche Begrünung der Abraumhalden des Stein- und Braunkohlenbergbaus. *Ber. d. Rienh.-Tuxen-Ges.*, 7: 69-88.
- [9] Kompała A. 1997. Spontaniczne procesy sukcesji na terenach po eksploatacji piasku na obszarze województwa katowickiego *Przegląd Przyrodniczy* 7 (1/2):1 63.
- [10] Krzaklewski W. 1979. Fitosocjologiczna metoda oceny warunków rekultywacji i zagospodarowania leśnego nieużytków na przykładzie skarp zwałowiska Kopalni Węgla Brunatnego Adamów, *Arch. Ochr. Środ.* 3-4: 1-121.
- [11] Matuszkiewicz W. 1986. Przewodnik do oznaczania zbiorowisk roślinnych Polski ("Guidebook to plant communities in Poland"). Państwowe Wydawnictwo Naukowe, Warszawa.
- [12] Mirek Z., Piękoś – Mirek H., Zajac A., Zajac M. 1995. Vascular plants of Poland a checklist. *Polish Botanical Studies*. No 15, Kraków.
- [13] Rostański A. 1996. Hałdy przemysłowe – uciążliwy, a zarazem interesujący element krajobrazu Górnego Śląska. *Przegląd Przyrodniczy*. 7(3-4): 259-262.
- [14] Rostański A. 1997a. Rośliny naczyniowe terenów o wysokim stopniu skażenia metalami ciężkimi. *Acta Biol. Siles.* 30(47): 56-85.
- [15] Rostański A. 1997b. Flora spontaniczna hałd Górnego Śląska. *Archiwum Ochrony Środowiska*. 23(3-4): 159-165.
- [16] Rostański A. 1998a. Anthropophytes and apophytes in colonization process on the post-industrial heaps in Upper Silesia Region. *Phytocoenosis* 10(9): 199-202.

- [17] Rostański A. 1998. Spontaneous flora on coal spoil heaps in Upper Silesia (Poland). In: Sarsby R.W. (Ed.), Contaminated and derelict land. The proceedings of Green 2: the second international symposium on Geotechnics Related to the Environment held in Kraków, Poland, September 1997: 488-491. Thomas Telford, London.
- [18] Rostański A. 2000a. Rekultywacja i zagospodarowanie nieużytków przemysłowych - rozwiązania alternatywne. Inżynieria ekologiczna. Nr 1. Ochrona i rekultywacja gruntów. Wyd. Ekoinżynieria, Lublin: 81-86.
- [19] Rostański A. 2000b. Podsumowanie badań flory terenów przemysłowych na Górnym Śląsku (1989-1999). Acta Biol. Siles. 35(52): 131-154.
- [20] Rostański A. 2000c. Trawy spontanicznie zasiedlające nieużytki przemysłowe w aglomeracji katowickiej. Łąkarstwo w Polsce. 3: 141-150.
- [21] Rostański A. 2001. Rola lokalnych zasobów genowych w zagospodarowaniu nieużytków przemysłowych. Materiały Sympozjum Warsztaty 2000 nt. Zagrożeń naturalnych w górnictwie. Wieliczka 29 maja – 1 czerwca 2001. "Druk-Rol", Kraków: 163-172.
- [22] Rostański A., Trueman I. 2001. A comparison of the spontaneous floras of coal mine heaps in two European industrial regions - Upper Silesia (Southern Poland) and the Black Country (UK). In: Green 3. The exploitation of natural resources and the consequences. Thomas Telford, London: 561-566.
- [23] Szafer W., Pawłowski B., Kulczyński S. 1986. Rośliny Polskie. PWN, Warszawa.
- [24] Szewo J., Woźniak G., Kubajak A., Wypało H., Rak W. 1995. Ścieżki dydaktyczne po terenach rekultywowanych - Kopalnia piasku Szczkowa S.A. Planta, Jaworzno-Szczakowa.
- [25] Tokarska-Guzik B., Rostański A., Klotz S. 1991. Roślinność hałdy pocynkowej w Katowicach -Welnowcu. Acta Biol. Siles. 19(36): 94-102.
- [26] Trzczińska-Tacik H. 1966. Flora i roślinność zwałów Krakowskich Zakładów Sodowych. – Fragm. Flor. Geobot. 12, 3: 243-318.
- [27] Wilkoń-Michalska J., Sokół M. 1969. Flora zwałów wapiennych Inowrocławskich i Janikowskich Zakładów Sodowych. – Zesz. Nauk. UMK Nauki Mat.-Przyrod. 21 Biologia 11: 173-208.
- [28] Woźniak G. 1998a. Plant succession on sedimentation pools in Upper Silesia.; In: Sarsby R. W. [Ed.] Contaminated and derelict land. The proceeding of Green 2: the second international symposium on Geotechnics Related tom the Environment held in Kraków, Poland, September 1997: Thomas Telford, London: 60-62.

- [29] Woźniak G. 1998b. Primary succession on the sedimentation pools of coal mine. In: J.B. Faliński, W. Adamowski, B. Jackowiak [Eds.] Synanthropization of plant cover in new Polish research. *Phytocoenosis* 9(10): 189-198.
- [30] Woźniak G. 2000. Rola procesów naturalnych w rekultywacji nieużytków przemysłowych. Wyd. Ekoinżynieria Lublin, Inżynieria ekologiczna 1: 87-93.
- [31] Woźniak G. 2001. Flora roślin naczyniowych osadników ziemnych wód kopalnianych-nieużytków poeksploatacyjnych na terenie Górnego Śląska. (Vascular plants flora of the coal mine underground water sedimentation pools - post-industrial wastelands in the Upper Silesia). *Materiały i Opracowania Centrum Dziedzictwa Przyrody Górnego Śląska*. p.48.

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